

REFLECTION INTERACTION IN THE TRANSVERSE DIRECTION OF A PLATE CAUSED BY PLANE IMPACT

V. A. Polyakov

University of Latvia, Institute of Polymer Mechanics, Riga, LV-1006, Latvia

KEYWORDS: short-term impact, plane stress wave, analytic continuation, method of characteristics, transverse stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Analytical study of dynamic stresses in a layered structure under a short-term impact in essence should be ascribed to the examination of unsteady-state process. Most of all it is based on the sequential solution of wave equation for every layer over the time interval of contact interaction between the structure and the striker. After the striker rebounded from the structure a harmonizable process is established which can be described by means of eigenmodes of the structure but for homogeneous material only. In the case of layered structure the analysis of numerical solutions is obtainable by methods of harmonic analysis [1]. The solutions represented as a series are not necessarily convenient for engineering analysis owing to the necessity of calculation of discontinuity in stresses of wave nature. After a recoil mass the simplifying idealization of the wave travels by multiple reflection normal to the surface of layered structure can be used at least for one-dimensional wave problem that is still solvable by characteristics. For a pulse loading with the plane front of a wave the duration of the pulse is small (less than time of wave travel across a doubled layer thickness). It is essentially to note, that in this case the study of transverse normal stress variation reduces to the wave travels by multiple transmission and reflection at contact layer surfaces [2].

The contact impact of mass, as a rule, is not pertinent to such case. It is known [3], that with the open back section of a uniform bar (or the back face of a uniform plate) the time of shock contact equals the time of the first cycle $\Delta t = 2l/a$, where $a = \sqrt{E/\rho}$, and l is the bar length or plate thickness. In the case of a back surface rigidly fixed, that resulting in maximum wave stresses, the contact time, during which the process of impact is considered, can not be usually represented by an explicit analytical expression. The exception is the time up to contact rebound with comparatively small mass during the second cycle [4].

The impact in the presence of gravitational mass attracts the attendant circumstance to invoke mass forces. In the latter case a non-uniform equation and a non-uniform boundary condition should state the wave problem. The solution in series evaluating critical contact time, that gives the time interval on which the wave problem is defined, presents difficulties to analyze still for the uniform bar under a big impact mass. The method of analytical continuation of the solution through characteristics is used here in an effort to deduce an analytical solution. The solution of non-uniform problem applicable to shock-excitation by mass over one of the plate surfaces with the other fixed and mass attraction is derived by a recursive procedure. The solution can be continued till arbitrarily remote time cycle. The critical time of contact can be found within the bounds of corresponding interval.

DYNAMIC RELATIONSHIPS IN TERMS OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR THREE -LAYER MEDIA

Interaction of stress waves in a layered structure for one dimensional along a spatial coordinate problem is expressible in terms of characteristics. Here we examine the basic relationships and dynamic equation for a sandwich structure under the plane front of transverse waves caused by an impact of arbitrary mass on the upper surface of the structure for all that the lower surface resting on a rigid foundation (see Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Sketch of three-layer media subjected to a plane surface impact.

The solution for the lower layer shows the only one function of two characteristics upon condition that the lower surface displacement is zero. Thus the displacements in the third layer may be expressed as

$$u_3(x, t) = \varphi(t - x/a_3) - \varphi(t + x/a_3) \quad (1)$$

From here on we shall use the following parameters dependent on Young modulus, specific density and layer thickness E_i , ρ_i , l_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$:

$$a_i = \sqrt{\frac{E_i}{\rho_i}}, \quad n_{21} = \sqrt{\frac{E_2 \rho_2}{E_1 \rho_1}}, \quad n_{32} = \sqrt{\frac{E_3 \rho_3}{E_2 \rho_2}},$$

$$k_1 = -(1 + n_{21})(1 + n_{32})/4, \quad k_3 = (1 + n_{21})(1 - n_{32})/4$$

$$k_2 = -(1 - n_{21})(1 - n_{32})/4, \quad k_4 = (1 - n_{21})(1 + n_{32})/4 \quad (2)$$

The other four functions for the remaining layers (two by two for the first and the second layer each) can be found by means of the function $\varphi(x, t)$ with the help of four conditions of layer contact in displacements and stresses at $x_c = l_3$, and $x_c = l_2 + l_3$. Taking respectively each layer characteristics $t \mp x/a_i$ as arguments of the function f_i^- for a forward wave and f_i^+ for a back wave the contact conditions in stresses will appear as:

$$\sqrt{E_i \rho_i} \frac{d}{d\zeta} (f_i^+ - f_i^-) \Big|_{x_c} = \sqrt{E_{i+1} \rho_{i+1}} \frac{d}{d\zeta} (f_{i+1}^+ - f_{i+1}^-) \Big|_{x_c} \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

where differentiating is effected with respect to the characteristic $\zeta = t \pm x/a_i$ and in displacements:

$$f_i^- + f_i^+ = f_{i+1}^- + f_{i+1}^+ \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (4)$$

Omitting intermediate calculations the functions f_i^{+-} , $i = 1, 2$ in terms of φ right now one pointed out that there were certain formalities to be observed regarding the characteristics inclusive the additional constants in the form of l_i/a_i . Derivation of function $\varphi(t \mp x/a_i)$ reduces to the last and most complicate stage for the mathematical derivation to describe the loading of an upper layer face surface with a striking mass. The contact stresses and acceleration of a mass at the surface have been derived in the form:

$$\sigma_1(t, l) = \sqrt{E_1 \rho_1} \sum_{j=1}^4 k_j [\varphi'(t + T_j) + \varphi'(t - T_j)]$$

$$\frac{d^2 u_1(t, l)}{dt^2} = \sum_{j=1}^4 k_j [\varphi''(t + T_j) - \varphi''(t - T_j)] \quad (5)$$

Where $l = l_1 + l_2 + l_3$ and a prime means differentiation with respect to characteristic and the shift of time has been defined by the following half-cycles

$$T_1 = l_1/a_1 + l_2/a_2 + l_3/a_3, \quad T_2 = T_1 - 2l_2/a_2,$$

$$T_3 = T_1 - 2l_3/a_3, \quad T_4 = T_1 - 2(l_2/a_2 + l_3/a_3) \quad (6)$$

It only remains to compose the balance of forces at the surface $x = l$ acting from the striking mass ($M\ddot{u}_1$) and its weight (Mg) under a vertical impact as well as surface response ($-S\sigma_1$), where S - surface area. So it has been obtained:

$$k_j \left\{ \varphi''(z_j) - \varphi''(z_j - 2T_j) + \frac{a_1}{ml_1} [\varphi'(z_j) + \varphi'(z_j - 2T_j)] \right\} = g \quad (7)$$

where $z_j = t + T_j$, $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, g - acceleration of gravity and $m = \frac{M}{\rho_1 S l_1}$.

Before procedure declaration of the solution of Eqn (7) the initial conditions for every layer should be analyzed:

$$u_i(0, x) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial u_i(0, x)}{\partial t} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (8)$$

Let us consider the displacement in Eqn (8) as a function of $\varphi(\zeta)$ with variable characteristics $\zeta = t \pm x/a_i$ at $t = 0$ within the limits $x_i^{\min}/a_i \leq |\zeta| \leq x_i^{\max}/a_i$, thereupon we are able to verify that over this range $\varphi \equiv 0$. The duration of the lowest-useful interval with this zero function is l_i/a_i . The part of summands in the right side of Eqn (5) equals zero at $t = 0$. As time passes $t > 0$ in the right - hand side of Eqn (5) the summands with the argument $t + T_i$ are nonzero values and furthermore the summands with the argument $t - T_j$ become nonzero values only at appropriate time. Thus the Eqn (7) describing an impact is given by expandable architecture of the summands varying in time. The additional summand with the coefficient k_j enters the left-hand side of Eqn (7). The solution process begins with the generalized coordinate z_j such that at the instant $t = 0$ the impact of mass M with a velocity V_0 initiates. The recursive procedure of solution analytic continuation at k_j is

“united” with the similar one at k_{j+1} next nearest. The initial conditions of Cauchy immediate task for the attached solution are taken from the previous solution. One must just note that the forth recursive procedure is not necessary due to the fact that it is resulted from Eqn (7) directly after the prior tree continued solutions have obtained.

For the degeneration into a uniform across thickness layered structure the relative parameters $n_{21} = n_{32} = 1$, $k_1 = -1$, $k_i = 0$, $i = 2,3,4$ take place and the Eqn (7) degenerates into the following:

$$\varphi''(\zeta) + \frac{a_1}{ml_1} \varphi'(\zeta) = \varphi''(\zeta - 2T_1) - \frac{a_1}{ml_1} \varphi'(\zeta - 2T_1) - g \quad (9)$$

With differentiation with respect to $a_1 t \pm x$ in place of differentiation with respect to the characteristics $t \pm x/a_1$ the Eqn (9) goes into the Eqn (6) from [5] cited lower.

WAVE INTERACTION IN A FINITE BAR UNDER IMPACT ACTION MASS AND GRAVITATIONAL FIELD

The complicated solution version related to nonuniform layered structure is omitted here and the problem in case of homogeneous plate is considered. The solution on this occasion could be used for the rough estimate of wave stresses in the core when $l_1/a_1, l_3/a_3 \ll l_2/a_2$ and $\sqrt{E_1 \rho_1}, \sqrt{E_3 \rho_3} \gg \sqrt{E_2 \rho_2}$. In doing so the problem set up for a plate under plane wave action is reduced to a bar model.

The solution includes the analytic evaluation of the cycle number wherein the recoil of a striker takes place dependent on the mass ratio of a striker and plate as well as an initial impact velocity. The novelty consists of the closed form solution for arbitrary time up to the point of the recoil of a striking mass considering gravitational force. The influence of gravity acceleration was demonstrated to offer different solutions for maximum velocity, initial stresses and contact duration in the cases of mass percussion on the upper or the lower plate surface (vertical impact from above or from below). The solution under the aforesaid condition has been represented as

$$u = \varphi(at - x) - \varphi(at + x) + \frac{gx(2l - x)}{2a^2} \quad (10)$$

The initial conditions given by Eqn (8) at $t = 0$ demonstrate the function $\varphi(x) = \varphi(-x)$ and its derivative $\varphi'(x) = \varphi'(-x)$ to be the even functions at least on open interval $0 < x < l$. Then over the interval $\varphi(x) = C$ is the case only and with the boundary condition $\varphi = 0$ at $x = 0$ in Eqn (10) $C = 0$ can be taken. Note that the argument of the even function considered here ought to be any number falling into the interval $(-l, l)$. So the initial function is $\varphi(\zeta) = 0$ at $-l < \zeta < l$.

With the aim of analytical continuation of the function $\varphi(\zeta)$ beyond the domain of the argument indicated above, that is definition $\varphi(\zeta)$ at $\zeta \geq l$, the boundary load condition given by Eqn (9) can be rewritten in terms of characteristics $at + l$ and $at - l$. Setting the first argument varies depending on time t as $\zeta = at + l$ the Eqn (9) can be transformed as

$$\varphi''(\zeta) + \frac{1}{ml} \varphi'(\zeta) = \varphi''(\zeta - 2l) - \frac{1}{ml} \varphi'(\zeta - 2l) - \frac{g}{a^2} \quad (11)$$

where all primes will be applied to differentiation with respect to ζ .

Note here again that the function φ defined from Eqn (11) is modifiable depending on the argument ζ and its domain boundaries are what matters solely. The limitless growth of the argument under limited bar length l is actually occurred through extension of time. In this respect the argument ζ is a “time” that. Moreover any combination of the time and spatial coordinates represented as $\zeta = at \pm x$ and falling into the domain of a given function φ offers the argument thereof.

First cycle of the contact of a bar with a mass

The integral of the Eqn (6) at $l \leq \zeta \leq 3l$ should present no problems and when taken into account that $\varphi(\zeta - 2l) \equiv 0$ as well as $\varphi(l) = 0$, $\varphi'(l) = V_0 / a$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1(\zeta) &= -\frac{gml}{a^2}(\zeta - l) + ml \left(\frac{V_0}{a} + \frac{gml}{a^2} \right) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\zeta-l}{ml}} \right) \\ \varphi'_1(\zeta) &= \left(\frac{V_0}{a} + \frac{gml}{a^2} \right) e^{-\frac{\zeta-l}{ml}} - \frac{gml}{a^2}, \quad l \leq \zeta < 3l \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

In the context of our further interest in a quick recoil due to impact pulse, we shall deduce limitations on the initial velocity and mass of a striker such that its separation from the bar takes place in the time interval less than one cycle duration. In this case the impact pulse arising from stresses at the contact surface is only dependent on characteristic $at + l$ referring to primary incident wave as the back wave occurring in the first cycle only after reflection from the fixing point will not reach yet the impact mass.

At given striker and bar mass ratio and time of their contact the limitations on the initial velocity shall be derived from the absence of compression at a contact point for the instant t_1^* , that is $u'_x(x=l) = 0$. From the latest condition on account of Eqns (10), (12) follows $t_1^* = (ml/a) \ln(1 + \chi)$. If one proposes to put the time of quick recoil $t_1^* < 2l/a$, the limitation on mass ratio at a given velocity is imposed by the following constraint

$$m \ln(1 + \chi) < 2, \quad \chi = \frac{aV_0}{mgl} \quad (13)$$

Exponentiation of Eqn (13) gives the limitation on velocity at a given mass ratio

$$V_0 < \frac{mgl}{a} (e^{\frac{2}{m}} - 1) \quad (14)$$

Should the interval $2l/a$ is multiple contact time, then $t_1^* = \frac{2l}{ak}$ and at $k = 1, 2, \dots$ the duration of an impact pulse causes the reduction in the initial velocity

$$V_0 = \frac{mgl}{a} (e^{\frac{2}{km}} - 1), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (15)$$

With a mutual reduction in m proportionally with the fall in contact time the initial velocity of impact will be reduced in equal ratio. The initial stress at the contact surface with area S by Eqn (15) equals

$$\sigma_0 = -V_0 \sqrt{E\rho} = -\frac{Mg}{S} \left(e^{\frac{2}{km}} - 1 \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (16)$$

The velocity V_0 in Eqn (16) is taken with minus sign as the bar is impacted upwards on its lower end. Should we change the direction of impact and displace a fixing point to a lower end the inequality (13) at $\chi < 0$ does not take place and the mass does not bounce off on the first time cycle. It is worthy of note here that the solution of the similar impact problem with open back surface when $u'_x(0, t) = 0$ leads to identical results for the quick recoil time of mass over the first cycle. As a consequence, any degree of fixity of a back surface – from zero to infinity - may be thought of as leaving the parameters of a quick recoil on the first cycle unchanged. In the event that a plane impact occurs normal with respect to a layer system, the pulse may be approximately substituted for well-defined stress σ_0 acted for a time $t_1^* = 2l/(ak)$ and calculated from Eqn (16) at reasonably large k . Moreover let one has calculated the pulse with help of Eqn (12):

$$J = \int_0^{t_1^*} \sigma|_{x=l} dt = -\int_0^{t_1^*} \varphi'_1(at+l) dt = \frac{gml}{a^2} \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{aV_0}{gml} \right) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{at_1^*}{ml}} \right) \right] \quad (17)$$

The higher approximation to the stress as generating the pulse Eqn (17) is obtainable by averaging Eqn (17) over the time right up to the recoil and taking into account the velocity Eqn (15):

$$\langle \sigma_0 \rangle = J / t_1^* = -\sigma_{st} \left[(km/2)(e^{2/km} - 1) - 1 \right] \quad (18)$$

where static stress $\sigma_{st} = Mg/S$. Expanding Eqn (16) and Eqn (18) into a power series at larger k it is easy to verify that $\sigma_0 / \langle \sigma_0 \rangle = 2$ and $\langle \sigma_0 \rangle = -gl\rho/k$.

The effects of the reduced initial velocity $V_* = aV_0 / gl$ of the percussion mass on the ratio $\tau = t_1^* a / 2l$ and the parameter m were shown in Fig. 2. *a, b*. This velocity has increased dramatically when the mass was to be on the decrease and with an increase of the recoil time in the first cycle.

Fig. 2. Variation of the reduced initial velocity of an impact mass on its relative value and stick duration in the first cycle. *a*: $m < 0.5$, *b*: $m > 0.5$

The stress can be taken into account in strength analysis under vibrations when m ratio is sufficiently small and accordingly the velocity of a striker is sufficiently large. If not, at the impact up to the recoil of a striker, the stresses in the cycles which follow the first cycle should be calculated.

Second cycle of the contact of a bar with a mass

The solution of function $\varphi_2(at \mp x)$ on the second time interval $2l/a \leq t \leq 4l/a$ ought to be gained by analytical continuation of $\varphi_1(at \mp x)$ on the first interval $0 \leq t \leq 2l/a$. Let the time in the range of those intervals was denoted as t_1 and t_2 accordingly. On the second interval the strain at the end $x = l$ is derived from [5] as function of t_1 :

$$\left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right|_{x=l} = -\varphi'_1(at_1 + l) - \varphi'_2(at_1 + l) \quad (19)$$

Rewriting the last expression in view of [5] was finally derived:

$$\left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right|_{x=l} = -3\varphi'_1(at_1 + l) - [\varphi'_1(3l) - \varphi'_1(l)]e^{-\frac{at_1}{ml}} + \frac{2}{ml}I_0(at_1 + l) \quad (20)$$

at that

$$I_0 = e^{-\zeta l/ml} \int_l^\zeta e^{y/ml} \varphi'_1(y) dy \quad (21)$$

Calculations of Eqns (20),(21) with the help of Eqn (12) finally give the expression of a strain at the contact surface during the second cycle and depending on the time of first cycle

$$\frac{\partial u(t_1, l)}{\partial x} = -\left(\frac{V_0}{a} + \frac{gml}{a^2} \right) \left(2 + e^{-\frac{2}{m}} - \frac{2at_1}{ml} \right) e^{-\frac{at_1}{ml}} + \frac{gml}{a^2} \left(1 + 2e^{-\frac{at_1}{ml}} \right) \quad (22)$$

The instant, when mass breaks away from the bar over the interval of the second cycle – (a quick recoil) can be deduced from the expression (22) set equal to zero:

$$2 + e^{-2/m} - \frac{2at_1}{ml} = \frac{2\left(\frac{1}{m} + e^{\frac{at_1}{ml}}\right)}{1 + \chi}, \text{ and } \chi = \frac{V_0 a}{mgl} \quad (23)$$

Notice that the parameter χ signed (+) enters the denominator on the right of (23). This is in the agreement with a weighty mass compressing impact on the lower end of a vertical bar. When the bar is revolved through 180° around a fixing point $x=0$ and the upper end is impacted, the parameter χ changes its sign as the positive axis direction and vector g are oppositely oriented.

In the recoil over the second time interval the impact initial velocity depends on mass relation and in this case Eqn (23) should be rewritten as a resolved velocity

$$V_* = \frac{V_0 a}{gl} = \frac{m(2 + e^{\frac{at_1}{ml}})}{2 + e^{-\frac{2}{m}} - \frac{2at_1}{ml}} - m, \quad 0 < t_1 < \frac{2l}{a} \quad (24)$$

There were shown the effects of the reduced initial velocity $V_* = aV_0 / gl$, of the percussion mass and the ratio of this mass to the bar mass $m = M_{st} / m_{bar}$ on the critical time of the recoil during the second cycle, see Fig. 3. Here the recoil time is $t_2^* = 2l/a + \tau_1^*(m, V_0)$ and the per-unit recoil time τ is in keeping with the recoil time in the second cycle t_2 as $t_2 = (2l/a)(1 + \tau)$.

Fig. 3. Reduced initial velocity of vertical impact from below (region from the right of a slot) and from above (region from the left of a slot) versus mass ratio m and per-unit recoil time τ in the second cycle.

Here one can note that the medial line $m \sim \tau$ between slot cut faces in Fig. 3 is the limit line along which the velocity is not defined. Allowing for $g \neq 0$ the nonremovable discontinuity of $V_* = f(m, \tau)$ takes place along this medial line. The aforesaid relation $m \sim \tau$ without taking a gravitational acceleration g into consideration has been obtained under horizontal impact [4]. Moreover, for greater velocities $V_0 \gg gml/a$ the right-hand side of Eqn (23) may be ignored and the solution agrees with one given in [4] where a gravitation force field has been excluded from the scope of work. Again, in this limiting case the upper limit of mass ratio $m^* = 1,73$ defining the feasibility of the model till a recoil time on the second cycle is readily obtainable.

CONCLUSIONS

- Governing relationships for plane waves of displacements and stresses propagating perpendicularly to the interfaces of a sandwich structure have been obtained by characteristics. The technique is applicable to the analytic treatment of the interaction of stress waves both in contact loads and in the fields of mass forces (kind of gravitational).
- The analytical approach using characteristics of the wave equation as applied to a homogeneous bar was advanced for the solution continuation on the first and second time intervals taking into consideration mass forces field. The influence of gravity acceleration was demonstrated to offer different solutions for maximum velocity and contact duration in the cases of mass percussion on the upper or the lower plate surface.

REFERENCES

1. Liu, G. R. and Xi, Z. C. "*Elastic Waves in Anisotropic Laminates*", CRC PRESS, Boca Raton, London-New York-Washington, 2002, p.452.
2. Polyakov, V.A., Shlitsa, R.P., Khitrov, V.V., and Zhigun, V.V., "Waves of Transverse Stresses Under a Plane Impact on the Surface of Sandwich Panel (Acoustic Approximation)", *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Vol. 38, No. 3, 2002, pp. 223-232.
3. Koshlakov, N., Gliner, E., and Smirnov, M., "*Mathematical Physics Equations in Partial Derivatives*", Ed., Higher School, Moscow, 1970, p. 712. (in Russian).
4. Rabotnov, Yu.N., "*Mechanics of Solid Body*", Ed., "Nauka", Moscow, 1979, p. 744 (in Russian).
5. Polyakov, V. A., Shlitsa, R. P., Khitrov, V. V. and Zhigun, V. I., "A study on the propagation of plane stress waves across the thickness of a plate by the method of analytic continuation in time", *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Vol. 40, No. 5, 2004, pp. 365-376.